

The Isomeric Transformation of *Allo*-cinnamylidene Acetic acid into the normal Form with Iodine as Photo-catalyst.

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Liebermann (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1446) discovered that *allo*-furfuraldehyde acrylic acid, *allo*-cinnamic acid and *allo*-cinnamylidene acetic acid are slowly transformed into the normal form under the influence of light but if iodine is simultaneously present the transformation is very rapid. He postulated the following mechanism for the transformation of *allo*-furfuraldehyde acrylic acid :

It will be noticed that the intermediate compounds I and II contain asymmetric carbon atoms, and it was

believed that the influence of polarised light on the velocity of this type of isomeric transformation, where asymmetric carbon atoms are present in the intermediate compound, might yield interesting results. The transformation of *allo*-cinnamylidene acetic acid into the normal form has been studied and it has been found that the velocity of transformation in chloroform solution is dependent on the intensity of light but not on its state of polarisation.

Allo-cinnamylidene acetic acid, $C_6H_5CH:CH.CH:CH.COOH$ was prepared according to Liebermann's method (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1441). He found that 0.6 grams of *allo*-acid and 0.1 gram of iodine dissolved in 12 c.c. of benzene exposed to mid-day sun gave crystals of normal acid in a minute, which, being difficultly soluble, separated out from benzene. Benzene, however, cannot be used as solvent in our experiments for two reasons :

(i) The separation of the end product as an insoluble solid would not be a case of photo-catalysis in homogeneous system.

(ii) The appearance of shining crystals of the normal acid, growing in size and depositing on the sides of the vessel, would very considerably change the intensity of the incident light by reflection and scattering and hence would make useless and unreliable all attempts to measure the amount of light absorbed by the reacting system.

The normal acid is sparingly soluble in most organic solvents; in chloroform, however, both the forms are fairly soluble and the velocity of isomeric transformation was measured in this solvent. Estimation of the quantity of the *allo*-form which has been changed in a definite interval of time to the normal form presented considerable difficulty. The normal acid has the melting point 165° , while the *allo*-acid has the melting point 136°

and it was thought that the quantity of each variety present in the solid residue after evaporation of chloroform in the dark might be found out by determining the melting point of the solid residue. This method was, however, found to be unreliable as the melting point of the mixture was not at all sharp. The following method of estimation was, however, found to yield satisfactory results. 3 c. c. of the chloroform solution containing the *allo*-acid and iodine were taken out from the reaction cell and the time noted. It was poured into a long stoppered tube with a bulb at one end which contained perfectly anhydrous sodium thiosulphate. The iodine reacted on shaking with sodium thiosulphate and the solution became colourless. The chloroform was then evaporated in an air-oven whose temperature was never allowed to exceed 70°. Liebermann found that a benzene solution of the *allo*-form containing iodine, if boiled in a water-bath for half an hour, gives normal acid. The chloroform solution, when freed from iodine, did not, however, during the process of evaporation, produce any measurable quantity of normal acid as will be clear from the fact that very good monomolecular velocity coefficients could be obtained from the experimental data. Moreover, the velocity of this photochemical transformation is very much slower in chloroform than in benzene.

Pure and dry benzene was now poured over the solid residue in the bulb tube up to a mark in the stem, (vol. 4 c. c.) the stopper put on, and the tube shaken in a thermostat for an hour, and left undisturbed to obtain clear benzene solution. 2 c. c. of the benzene solution was sucked out by means of a pipette, fitted with glass-wool plug and the quantity of the total acid in the solution obtained by titration with fresh NaOH solution. The solubility of the normal acid in benzene at different temperatures was determined, from which

the quantity of the normal acid which passed into solution at the temp. of the thermostat could be determined. The solubility data in benzene are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Temp.	Gm. of normal acid in 1 c.c. of benzene $\times 10^3$
15°C	4.26
22°	5.29
30°	7.72
35°	10.0

The difference between the total acid and the normal acid gives the quantity of the *allo*-acid that has remained unchanged. It is essential for the success of the experiments that both sodium thiosulphate and benzene should be perfectly dry. Crystals of pure sodium thiosulphate were powdered and heated in an air-oven at 110° for several hours and kept in a vacuum dessicator over sulphuric acid. Iodine and chloroform were purified in the usual way.

A 1000 c.p. Pointolite lamp maintained by a constant current of 6.5 amperes was used as the source of light. The point arc, placed at the focal length of a powerful converging lens, gave a parallel beam of light which was passed successively through filters of *N*-KNO₃ solution (1 cm. thick) and 0.1*N*-CuSO₄ solution (10 cms. thick). The reaction vessel was maintained at a constant temp. by enclosing it in a double jacketed metal box with a window, through whose annular space water from a thermostat was circulated by a pump. The temperature of this jacket could be maintained constant within $\pm 1^\circ$.

The experimental results are given below.

TABLE II

Concn. of iodine 2.048×10^{-3} gm. mol. per litre

Initial Concn. of *allo*-acid..... 1.709×10^{-1} " " "

Temp. 34.3°C .

Time in mins.	Titre of NaOH sol. (.0126 N, equivalent to the concn. of <i>allo</i> -acid)	$k = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-c}$
0*	12.9 c.c.	—
124	8.8 c.c.	.00154
219	6 c.c.	.00151
297	4.6 c.c.	.00150
393	3.1 c.c.	.00156
		Mean .00153

The reaction gives a good monomolecular constant as will be clear from Table II. In Table III are given the velocity coefficients for different concentrations of iodine.

TABLE III

Concn. of iodine	Concn. of <i>allo</i> -acid	k (mean)
2.048×10^{-3}	1.709×10^{-1}	.00153
1.024×10^{-3}	"	.00152
$.4096 \times 10^{-3}$	"	.00153

* The first reading is taken after about 3 hours' exposure to light, when sufficient normal acid has been formed to give a saturated solution with benzene under the conditions of experiment, and this first reading in the table is given as corresponding to zero time.

It will be noticed from Table III that the velocity constants are independent of the concentration of iodine which is the photo-catalyst in the reaction. This is explicable only on the ground that the whole of the incident light within the photo-active region is absorbed by the lowest concentration of iodine used in our experiments. According to Plotnikow,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{k}{p} \left[1 - e^{-sp(a-x)} \right] (b-x) \quad \dots (1)$$

where $(a-x)$ is the concentration of the photo-active substance, $(b-x)$ that of the photo-inactive component.

Equation (1) reduces to

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{k}{p} (b-x) \doteq k'(b-x) \quad \dots (2)$$

if $e^{-sp(a-x)}$ is negligibly small or if variation in

$\left[1 - e^{-sp(a-x)} \right]$ is small.

$$\therefore k' = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{b}{b-x}$$

The extinction co-efficient of iodine in chloroform solution was measured by a Koenig Merten spectro-photometer and calculated from the equation

$$\frac{\log_{10} \tan a^1 - \log_{10} \tan a^2}{lc} = \epsilon$$

The values are given in the following table.

TABLE IV

Wave-length (λ)	Extinction co-efficient (ϵ)
6563	$\cdot 88 \times 10^3$
5876	$2 \cdot 1 \times 10^3$
5461	$5 \cdot 9 \times 10^3$
4861	$8 \cdot 9 \times 10^3$
4571	$4 \cdot 4 \times 10^3$

It will be seen that the extinction co-efficients have large values, and in our experiments with the lowest concentration of iodine the percentage of light absorbed are—

λ	Light absorbed
6563	86·2% apply.
5876	98·9% "
5461	100% "
4861	100% "
4571	100% "

Influence of Concentration of allo-acid on the Velocity Co-efficient.

The range of concentration available for experimental purpose is rather small due to the following reasons:—

(1) The limited solubility of the *allo-acid* in CHCl_3 .

(2) An appreciable solubility of the normal form in benzene in which the solid residue (a mixture of normal and *allo-acid*), on evaporation of chloroform, is dissolved for estimating the amount of *allo-acid* left over.

TABLE V

Initial concentration of *allo*-acid ... 3.418×10^{-1} gm. mols. per litre.
 Concentration of iodine ... 1.024×10^{-2} gm. mols. per litre.

Time in mins.	Titre of .0124 N— NaOH soln.	<i>k</i>
0	32.2	...
85	25.5	.00119
160	22.5	.00097
233	17.5	.00100
315	15	.00102
		Mean .00105

The agreement between the individual values of velocity co-efficients are not so good as recorded before, but the mean value of the co-efficient is certainly less than .00150 in Table II. This is an anomaly, for in homogeneous unimolecular reactions the velocity constant is independent of the concentration of the substance undergoing transformation. The reason for this anomaly must be sought for in the fact that Equation (1) is not strictly accurate. If it were so, the rate of photochemical transformation would increase indefinitely as the concentration of the photo-inactive component increases, although the amount of light absorbed remains constant. This would mean a complete negation of Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence, which has been found to be true in some cases at least. The equation of Cario (*Zeit. Physik*, 1922, 10, 185), modified by Turner (*Phys. Review*, 1924, 23, 466),

$$\text{Rate} = c \left[\frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{Aa^2rp}} \right]$$

$$\text{Whence } \frac{1}{\text{Rate}} = \frac{1}{\text{Const.}} + \frac{1}{\text{Const.} \times p} \dots \dots (4)$$

(where *p* is gas pressure of the photo-inactive component), which has been applied with success to photochemical

reaction in gaseous systems, gives a definite limiting value for the rate of transformation when the concentration of the acceptor molecules becomes infinite. According to Eq. (4) the increment in the value of $\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t}$ with increment in pressure becomes less and less as the absolute value of the pressure becomes larger and larger. The extension of this equation to homogeneous photochemical reaction in solution has been tried by the substitution of the osmotic pressure for concentration. The graph of the inverse of rate of transformation against the inverse of osmotic pressure of acceptor molecules will be a straight line, the inverse of intercept representing the limiting rate of reaction for infinite concentration of the photo-inactive component. The values of $\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t}$ cannot be very accurately determined for very small intervals of time because the method of estimation of the substance undergoing transformation is not at all sensitive in this case, but from Tables II and V we can obtain mean values of $\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t}$ for mean values of concentration of *allo*-acid. This is given in the following Table.

TABLE VI

Rate	$\frac{1}{\text{Rate}}$	Mean concn. of <i>allo</i> -acid	$\frac{1}{p}$ (p in millimetre)
·0605	16·53	27·35	$22·9 \times 10^{-5}$
·0495	20·63	20	$31·1 \times 10^{-5}$
·0371	26·95	10·6	$55·7 \times 10^{-5}$
·0241	41·49	7·2	$82·9 \times 10^{-5}$
·0180	55·56	5·3	117×10^{-5}
·0150	64	3·85	162×10^{-5}

In Fig. 1 the inverse of the rate has been plotted against inverse of osmotic pressure and if we omit the last point, *i.e.*, for the lowest concentration, all the points fall on a straight line; $1/\text{Rate}$ for infinite concn. of *allo*-acid is 7·5, or the rate of transformation is ·133 for infinite

concn. of *allo*-acid. It is rather unfortunate that the velocity of the reaction for higher concentrations of *allo*-acid is not capable of direct experimental measurement. From Cario and Turner's equation we can, however, calculate the life period of the excited molecule. Since,

$$\text{Rate} = c \left[\frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{Aa^2\tau p}} \right]$$

where a is the mean distance between the centres of molecules, τ the life period and A , a constant equal in magnitude to

$$2666 \cdot 6 \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta N}{k\theta} \cdot \frac{m_1 + m_2}{m_1 m_2}}$$

where m_1 and m_2 are the molecular weights of the photo-active and the acceptor molecules respectively, θ , the absolute temp. and k , the gas constant per molecule, it is evident that when $\frac{1}{\text{rate}}$ is plotted against $\frac{1}{p}$,

$$Aa^2\tau = \frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}} \text{ of the graph.}$$

The intercept is 7.5 and the slope = (4.5×10^4) and $A = 2.52 \times 10^{21}$.

Putting $a = 3 \times 10^{-8}$, $\tau = .8 \times 10^{-10}$ sec. This is slightly less than the life period of activated molecules by other methods and the average value is about 10^{-9} .

Application of Einstein's Law of Photo-Chemical Equivalence.

Radiant energy from a Hefner lamp at a distance of 1 metre produced a galvanometer deflection of 25 divisions. The light absorbed by the lowest concn. of iodine is equivalent to 689 divisions of galvanometer. The thickness of the reaction vessel used was 1 cm. Energy absorbed per sq. cm. per second

$$= \frac{689 \times 900}{25} \text{ ergs.}$$

Assuming the mean wave-length of efficient light to be $500\mu\mu$, $h\nu$ becomes 3.9×10^{-13} ergs.

Therefore the number of quanta in the absorbed energy = 6.35×10^{15}

The change in the *allo*-acid in 393 minutes (see Table II) in 1.5 c.c. of the solution corresponding to a surface of 1.5 sq. cm. = 9.8 c.c. of 0.0126*N* alkali.

Therefore, the number of molecules transformed per sec. per sq. cm.

$$= \frac{9.8 \times 0.0126 \times 6.3 \times 10^{15}}{60 \times 393 \times 1000 \times 1.5}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\text{The no. of quanta}}{\text{The no. of molecules}} = 2.8$$

that is, 2.8 quanta are necessary for the transformation of 1 molecule of *allo*-acid. For higher concentration of *allo*-acid change in 1.5 c.c. in 160 minutes = 9.7 c.c. of 0.0124*N* alkali (see Table V). Here 1.2 quanta transform 1 molecule of *allo*-acid. For infinite concentration of *allo*-acid, assuming that the extrapolation value is justified in Curve 1 :—

Change in *allo*-acid per minute = 1.33 c.c. of 0.0124*N* alkali. Hence one quantum transforms in the limiting case 1.8 molecules of *allo*-acid.

Temperature Co-efficient of the Reaction.

The velocity co-efficient of the reaction at 24.3° was found to be 0.0087, concentration of *allo*-acid being 1.709×10^{-1} gm. mol. per litre and that of iodine 1.024×10^{-2} gm. mols. per litre.

The temperature co-efficient is, therefore, $\frac{0.0152}{0.0087} = 1.75$

Influence of the State of Polarisation of Light on the Velocity Co-efficient.

The intensities of the parallel beams of ordinary light and plane polarised light were made approximately equal by suitable choice of lenses. The light filters used were always identical and in the case of ordinary light, a film of Canada balsam between two plane parallel glass plates, were interposed between the reaction cell and the source of light to compensate any effect that the film of Canada balsam in the Nicol might produce in the case of polarised light.

Intensity of incident plane polarised light

=234 divisions of galvanometer (a resistance of 33 ohms was in the circuit of the galvanometer).

Change in *allo-acid* in 10 hours=10·7 c.c.

Intensity of incident ordinary light under the same conditions=239 divisions.

Change in *allo-acid* in 10 hours=11 c.c.

In another set of experiments the intensities of plane polarised and circularly polarised light were similarly made almost equal. It was found that the velocity of transformation is independent of the quality of polarisation of absorbed light.

Intensity of plane polarised light (with 30 ohms resistance in the circuit of the galvanometer)=405 divisions.

Change in *allo-acid* in 10 hours=17·05 c.c.

Intensity of circularly polarised light under the same conditions=387 divisions.

Change in *allo-acid* in 10 hours=16·9 c.c.

Hence, there is practically no change in the velocity co-efficients due to the change in the state of polarisation of the incident light.

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